

Measuring Resident Attitudes with the Tourism Acceptance Score (TAS)

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Core results

A scale for assessing resident's evaluation of tourism is introduced resulting in a Tourism Acceptance Score.

It builds upon structural models of resident attitudes, but is more concise and therefore easier to implement.

The score takes two perspectives, Place and Personal.

Reference values are given for Germany.

The text provides concrete information on how to interpret the scores.

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Introduction

In a traditional perspective, the economic success of tourism destinations depends on visitor satisfaction and the quality of their experiences (Holden, 2006, S. 364). In recent years, however, resident's quality of life has moved into the focus of researchers and practitioners alike. This working paper is not the place to discuss all the origins and facets of this discussion. The interested reader is therefore directed to the growing body of literature on this topic (Butler, 2019; Hsu & Chen, 2019; Postma & Schmücker, 2017; Tse & Tung, 2022)

A central point for the discussion of the residents' perspective is their attitude towards tourism ("tourism acceptance"). An extensive body of research literature has been produced on this topic (Hadinejad et al., 2019). In the three journals *Annals of Tourism Research*, *Tourism Management* and *Journal of Travel Research* alone, 140 articles were published on this topic between 1984 and 2010 (Nunkoo et al., 2013). From 2011 to 2019, a further two articles with the title keywords "resident attitude" or "resident perception" were published in the *Annals*, 25 in *Tourism Management* and eleven in the *Journal of Travel Research*.

In destination management, a number of scales was introduced, but usually with not much theoretical background, so for Berne (Lehmann Friedli & Julen, 2019), Amsterdam (Gerritsma & Vork, 2017), Tyrol (Siller & Mitterer-Leitner, 2019) or Copenhagen (TCI Research & Wonderful Copenhagen, 2018).

In academia, multivariate approaches to the explanation of tourism acceptance through structural models were developed and operationalised (Gannon et al., 2020; Nunkoo & So, 2016; Su et al., 2020). The empowerment concept was originally developed in psychotherapy and, from the beginning of the 2000s, was adapted to

tourism research (Cole, 2006; Scheyvens, 1999, 2002; Sofield, 2003). Based upon this literature, Boley & McGehee finally developed their own scale: The Resident Empowerment through Tourism Scale (RETS) plays a special role because it is not only theoretically sound but also well tested for reliability and construct validity (Boley et al., 2014; Boley & McGehee, 2014). The authors specified four dimensions (psychological, social and political empowerment plus personal economic benefit) which they combined into one structural model (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Proposed model of empowerment's influence on resident attitudes towards tourism

Fig. 1. Proposed model of empowerment's influence on resident attitudes toward tourism; Note: * indicates that hypothesis has not been empirically tested in previous studies.

Source: Boley et al. (2014, p. 35)

The model defines the final construct, “support for tourism” as the result of weighing up positive and negative impacts of tourism. We transferred this idea to the development of the TAS scale.

TAS Scale

The central idea of the TAS scale is to weigh up the positive and negative effects of tourism. This idea was adopted from the “Support for Tourism” model by Boley & McGehee (2014, S. 35). However, unlike in the Boley & McGehee model, no unidirectional perspective (namely the “Support for Tourism”, which can be more or less pronounced) is adopted, but rather a balanced assessment of the effects of tourism from the perspective of the destination population.

A five-point ordinal scale with a natural centre point is used. The question stimulus is in the first perspective “How do you rate the impact of tourism on [name of the place of residence]?” and in the second perspective “How do you rate the impact of tourism on you personally?”. We call the aggregated result in the first perspective “Place TAS” and in the second perspective “Personal TAS”.

Figure 2: The TAS scale

How do you rate the impact of tourism on [name of place of residence]?	... you personally?
Mainly positive	[01]	[01]
Rather positive	[02]	[02]
Neutral	[03]	[03]
Rather negative	[04]	[04]
Mainly negative	[05]	[05]
Don't know	[99]	[99]

Answer options are “Mainly positive”, “Rather positive”, “Neutral”, “Rather negative”, and “Mainly negative”. In the survey material (paper

& pencil or online), the answer options are arranged in such a way that the order of the scale points is clear.

This scale is an ordinal scale that cannot be treated as (pseudo-) metric because the respondent cannot recognise that the scale points are meant to be equally spaced. In order to arrive at an easily comprehensible and easily comparable (total) acceptance value between different places of residence, the answers are offset so that a single value per perspective results for each scale (which, because it is an ordinal scale, must not be the arithmetic mean). For this purpose, the share values of the two natural halves of the scale are subtracted from each other, resulting in a balance value: The Tourism Acceptance Score (TAS).

The score is defined (according to the numbering in Figure 1) as the sum of the first two scale points minus the sum of the last two scale points, weighted by the total number of respondents:

$$TAS = \frac{(n[01] + n[02] - n[04] - n[05])}{n} \times 100$$

Statements at the scale point “Neutral” and drop outs (“Don’t know”) are not taken into account.

The resulting TAS can take values from –100 to +100. The term “proponents” refers to those who answer on the positive side of the scale after weighing up the results. “Opponents”, on the other hand, are those who answer on the negative side of the scale.

- With a TAS of 0, the number of proponents would be equal to the number of opponents.
- Positive TAS values describe a surplus of proponents.
- Negative TAS values describe a surplus of opponents.

The TAS is given in percentage points. In this respect, there are similarities with the concept of the Net Promoter Score (Freed, 2013; Reichheld, 2003) which is widely used in business practice. However, the TAS has the advantage of a natural neutral point: while the determination of the separation values for promoters and opponents in the Net Promoter Score is at the discretion of the scale developer, this separation is naturally predetermined in the scale presented here.

It is worth mentioning, that the terms “proponents” and “opponents” must not be understood here in a normative sense, for example that the proponents are in favour of a certain planning or development and the opponents are against it.

TAS Reference Values (Germany)

For Germany, Schmücker & Eisenstein (2021) found TAS scores of > + 50 for the place of residence perspective (Place TAS) and +27 in the personal perspective (Personal TAS). These values were drawn from a representative sample for Germany (with an average tourism intensity of 5.5 nights spent per inhabitant).

Looking at tourism intensive places (more than 20 nights spent per inhabitant), higher Place TAS (between 70 and 80) and somewhat lower Personal TAS values (between 10 and 20) were found. A more detailed analysis showed that the Place TAS becomes more positive when tourism intensity grows, while the Personal TAS remains more or less on the same level.

A positive correlation between the two perspectives was found: Respondents who have a positive evaluation of tourism impacts for the

place of residence also tend to have a positive evaluation for them personally, χ^2 (df=25, n = 3000) = 1020, $p < .001$; $r_t = .521$, $p < .001$.

Figure 3 shows a compilation of TAS valued for twelve cities/places. Although there are large individual differences, there is a pattern in the results with the Place TAS being usually positive and the Personal TAS being usually smaller or even negative. This is particularly true for places with high tourism intensities (intensities not shown in the figure).

Figure 3: Place and Personal TAS values for 12 cities/places

TAS Interpretation

Place TAS

The Place TAS can be interpreted as an indicator for the **quality of tourism destination management**. Negative values can mean:

- Too much tourism
- “Wrong” tourism (e.g. wrong target group characteristics, wrong target group behaviour)
- Possibly inadequate communication

If this TAS is negative (< 0), public tourism destination management has not worked well: Why should the public sector invest in tourism that, in the opinion of the people who live there, has more disadvantages than advantages for the place of residence? Consequence: change course

If this TAS is more negative than in the reference group, there is still potential for optimisation, by answering questions like: Why is that? What specific problems/disruptive factors are there? How can they be eliminated? Which better-suited target groups can be reached?

If this TAS is more positive than in the reference group, destination managers can concentrate on maintaining or expanding this competitive position.

Personal TAS

The Personal TAS can be seen as an indicator of the **distribution of the benefits and burdens of tourism**. A negative value can indicate a large-scale and/or permanent perception of disturbance that is not offset by any personal benefit. This can happen because disturbance is always personal, but benefit not necessarily. If this TAS is negative (< 0), more

residents personally experience disadvantages from tourism than other residents experience advantages. A continuation of this type of tourism will probably lead to rejection of tourists, tourism stakeholders and those responsible for politics. If this TAS is more negative than in the reference group, there is still potential for optimisation (see Place TAS). If this TAS is more positive than in the reference group, one can concentrate on maintaining or expanding this competitive position.

Difference between Place and Personal TAS

The difference between the Place and Personal TAS can be interpreted as a measure of **distance to or detachment from tourism** in the place of residence. This is because a big difference between the two perspectives means a big difference between “benefit/cost for the place” and “benefit/cost for me personally”. Usually, we see a growing distance between the two perspectives in places with high tourism intensity: Here, residents acknowledge the positive economic effect of tourism for the place of residence but with themselves frequently not profiting in the same way.

Crosstabulation of Place and Personal TAS

As was shown in the reference values section, a crosstabulation of the two perspectives shows a positive correlation (people who have a positive view on the Place perspective tend to have also a positive view on the Personal perspective).

Crosstabulation can also help to identify **clusters** of “true opponents” (seeing more disadvantages than advantages in both perspectives, red), “true proponents” (seeing more advantages than disadvantages in both perspectives, green) and groups in between, which can be indifferent or divided (high share of neutrals, grey). There are attempts to form additional target groups in the blue fields (“toleration”, “conditional

acceptance”), but these appear to be neither theoretically sound nor face-valid.

Figure 4: Crosstabulation of both perspectives

	Mainly positive	Rather positive	Neutral	Rather negative	Mainly negative
Mainly positive					
Rather positive					
Neutral					
Rather negative					
Mainly negative					

Amplitude Triangles

Closer examination of results reveals that in most cases the Personal TAS holds a higher share of neutral answers than the Place TAS. The higher the share of neutral answers, the smaller the space of options becomes (lighter coloured triangles in Figure 5). The distance of the diagonal from the origin can therefore be understood as the amplitude of the positive and negative answers.

The amplitude is simply the share of positive and negative answers combined:

$$Amplitude = \frac{(n[01] + n[02] + n[04] + n[05])}{n} \times 100$$

In the place perspective, the answers are generally more polarised, i.e. there are fewer neutrals than in the personal perspective. The light triangles and arrow lengths in the right-hand illustration symbolise this.

Figure 5: Amplitudes

It should be noted that the individual answer “neutral” can be the result of two different individual considerations:

- Perception of pronounced advantages and disadvantages that cancel each other out: “Neutral” with strong tourism impacts.
- Perception of no (or only a few) advantages and disadvantages, so that neither advantages nor disadvantages can be identified: “Neutral” with little or no tourism impact.

However, on aggregated level, different proportions of positive and negative answers can lead to the same TAS value. Here, a view at the amplitude can be helpful. With a large amplitude, there are many

respondents who see predominantly positive effects and many who see predominantly negative effects.

With a low amplitude, there are no (or few) respondents who see positive effects and no (or few) who see predominantly negative effects.

Figure 6: Five zone amplitude triangle

The amplitude can be interpreted as a measure of **involvement of the population**. With balanced TAS values around 0, a high amplitude can also be interpreted as a measure of polarisation.

Figure 6 shows these considerations combined into one picture. Only with high amplitudes, pronounced positive or negative TAS values are possible. The lower the amplitude, the narrower the range of options (light triangle). Four fields can be described from this, with the amplitude as a measure of the involvement of the population. With balanced TAS values, a high amplitude can also be interpreted as a measure of polarisation (dark square). The position of the reference lines will vary depending on the TAS being considered and depending on the reference group.

TAS Implementation considerations

The TAS questions were implemented both in paper & pencil questionnaires and in online surveys. There were no problems found in both formats. Personal interviews have not been tested, but seem also realistic.

In most practical cases, additional questions are asked in order to gain more information about the reasons behind the respondent's TAS answers, about his or her personal situation etc. However, these are additional aspects outside the scope of this working paper.

Because the TAS values cannot be calculated on individual level but only for groups of respondents, it has turned out to be practical to recode the data in the dataset into “+1” for proponents, “-1” for opponents” and “0” for neutrals and don't knows. Thus, the TAS can simply be computed as the mean of the recoded values.

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Notes

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